

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE/ELASTOMER
LAMINAR STRUCTURES

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The low frequency (0.08 Hz), high strain (200% to 450%) fatigue behavior of epoxy based organic polymer carbon filamentary composites has been determined in the context of their being combined with elastomeric layers to form lightweight, integrally damped composite laminar structures. To determine the dynamic shear fatigue properties of the composite to elastomer adhesive bonds, a double lap-shear type test specimen (ASTM D837-3) was employed (Figure 1). Various specimen types were fabricated whereby the laminate (unidirectional) plies were oriented at 0° (Type C-0°) and at 90° (Type C-90°) to the direction of the applied strain. For comparison purposes, elastomer to steel double lap shear specimens were also tested under the same conditions.

Cyclic loading curves were obtained on the specimens with the results being typified by Figure 2. Rather than analyzing the data obtained in a standard S-N curve fashion, an approach based on the successive energy dissipation (loss in elastic energy storage capacity) per cycle was used. In this case, the fraction of elastic energy dissipated or exhausted per cycle, dE_n/dc ($1/E_n$), was measured and plotted against the cycle number using the derived equation:

$$\frac{dE_n}{dc} \left(\frac{1}{E_n} \right) = 1 - \frac{f_n + 1}{f_n(a)}^{(a)}$$

where $f_n(a)$ is the maximum load in the nth cycle and E_n is the energy stored in the material deformed (a) units during the nth deformation cycle.

Employing this fatigue (Rheological Damage) analysis approach, a comparison of the data showed that the type C-0° and type S specimens were similar in their fatigue behavior (more abrupt failure characteristics) while the type C-90° showed a different fatigue behavior (more gradual failure characteristics). It appears then that the high strain fatigue behavior of carbon fiber/epoxy composite - elastomer laminar structures depends upon the orientation of the composite ply

at the interface. Microphotographic surface analysis techniques were employed to further understand the fatigue response behavior of these combined composite - elastomer structural systems. These observations were finally reviewed in terms of presently known theories for fatigue in rubber.¹⁻³

FIGURE 1: DIAGRAM OF FATIGUE SPECIMEN

FIGURE 2: LOAD VS. CYCLES DATA SHOWING LOAD DROP PRIOR TO FATIGUE FAILURE

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